

Independent Per-Phase Power Control in Four-Leg Grid-Following Voltage Source Converters

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Abstract—Distribution grids are facing a great transformation in recent years with the advent of smart grid technologies. Particularly, more and more controllable devices, based on power electronics, are being deployed in this part of the power system. These interfacing devices are in charge of the active power management of many energy resources ranging from renewable energy sources to energy storage systems. However, in addition to this, power electronics may provide valuable ancillary services for improving the operation of distribution networks. With this regard, it is important to stress that low-voltage distribution systems are by nature unbalanced due to single-phase loads. Therefore, the use of already installed voltage source converters for minimizing the network imbalance could be of interest to the Distribution System Operator. This paper proposes a per-phase independent power control of three-phase four-leg Voltage Source Converters for reducing network voltage imbalance. The control approach has been experimentally validated in a test bed to evidence the technical feasibility of the proposal.

Index Terms—Voltage Source Converters, distribution networks, imbalance mitigation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Distribution networks, particularly low-voltage (LV) ones, have been traditionally of minor significance compared to the transmission level. These usually deliver power to passive final users in a radial manner. Therefore, with appropriate planning procedures and some basic control actions in primary substations, it was possible to achieve a secure operation, i.e. nodal voltages and feeder currents within the technical limits. However, the rapid expansion of distributed energy resources (DERs) such as renewable generation, electric vehicles, and storage systems leads to new challenges in maintaining quality standards, service continuity, and security [1], [2]. Among them, the following can be highlighted:

- Change of role of end users from passive to active behavior. This is mainly because most DERs use voltage source converters (VSCs) as their grid connection interface. The high control capacity of these devices allows the user to participate in the control of the distribution network providing the so-called ancillary services [3], beyond just exchanging active power with it. These capabilities are essential for the Distribution System Operator (DSO), as they enable having more control assets in the network. [4].
- The integration of DERs leads to bidirectional power flows between transmission and distribution networks that can cause overloads in lines and transformers, as well as large daily voltage variations in some nodes of the network [5]. The existing control assets, mainly in the primary substation as commented above, would not be sufficient to avoid this type of disturbance.
- The replacement of electromechanical loads by non-linear loads based on power electronics increases the flexibility and operating performance of users. On the other hand, it introduces harmonic currents and imbalances that worsen the power quality of the network [6]–[8].
- At present, the level of real-time communication between the different assets is practically non-existent [9]. This is one of the most limiting drawbacks to the efficient use of new assets in the optimal operation and control of distribution networks.

All these issues are even more challenging in LV networks due to their unbalanced nature, lack of topological knowledge, and practically non-existent communication system, available only in the secondary substation [10]. Focusing on the unbalanced nature of LV networks opens up the discussion of whether VSC-based DERs could help improve the balance of these networks through their operation. There are emerging opportunities to balance three-phase DNs with a number of

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power electronic devices installed in the system [11]. In [12], the independent per-phase control capability of photovoltaic (PV) three-phase four-wire (3P-4W) inverters, which are able to inject different active and reactive powers in each phase, is explored to reduce the system phase unbalance. The benefits of this operation are analyzed by posing an optimization problem in a European LV network, where the independent per-phase control of three-phase PV inverters significantly improves the network performance, contributing to the increased penetration of DERs. Although this work proposes independent control of the power per-phase in 3P-4W VSCs, it does not discuss how to achieve this objective from a converter control point of view.

Taking into account the benefits that unbalanced operation of VSCs in LV distribution networks can provide, the main contribution of this paper is to propose a tailor-made control algorithm capable of reproducing any unbalanced condition in grid-following 3P-4W VSC. This approach is based on the creation of three virtual balanced three-phase systems for each phase of the VSC, which allows the implementation of classic active and reactive power control techniques.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II is devoted to providing the control algorithm of a 3P-4W VSC for achieving independent active and reactive power control per phase. Section III validates the proposed control algorithm through simulation results. Section IV evaluates the performance of the proposal in an experimental testbed. Finally, section IV closes the paper with the main conclusions and future work.

II. INDEPENDENT ACTIVE AND REACTIVE CONTROL PER PHASE

This section proposes a control algorithm for properly controlling in an independent way the active and reactive power in each phase of a 3P-4W VSC.

Fig. 1 represents a 3P-4W VSC with an LCL coupling filter. These devices must impose different active and reactive power injections per phase to achieve the stated objective. Note that the 3P-4W VSCs are controlled as current sources in grid-following mode and, therefore, adequate current references are required for controlling the desired powers. In case of balance conditions, these current references are set in a straightforward manner from the active and reactive power references either in the $\alpha\beta$ or dq domains using an instantaneous power formulation [13]. This is not the case,

Fig. 1. 3P-4W VSC with an LCL coupling filter.

however, for unbalanced situations since the instantaneous three-phase powers contain both constant and oscillating 100 Hz terms. Therefore, it is difficult to establish a mapping between the reference phase powers and the corresponding instantaneous power components required for the VSC current control.

For this reason, it is proposed to apply a control algorithm with an independent power control per phase. The proposed control strategy is based on the assumption that the 3P-4W VSC can be controlled as three independent single-phase devices, one per phase, with independent active and reactive power references. For doing so, it is proposed to generate a virtual three-phase system related to each phase of the 3P-4W VSC to take advantage of this characteristic of the balanced systems. To do this, the phase m voltage is associated with the α component of its virtual $\alpha\beta$ stationary frame, while its counterpart β component is obtained by delaying the α signal $\pi/2$ radians. This delay can be achieved in different ways [14], particularly this work has applied two cascaded low-pass filters tuned to the fundamental frequency ω for the voltage at the point of interconnection (POI):

$$v_{s,m\alpha} = v_{sm} ; v_{s,m\beta} = 2 \cdot \frac{\omega}{s + \omega} \cdot \frac{\omega}{s + \omega} v_{s,m\alpha} \quad \forall m = a, b, c \quad (1)$$

Note that these $v_{s,m\alpha}$ and $v_{s,m\beta}$ have the same amplitude with a delay of $\pi/2$ radians which corresponds to a balanced three-phase system.

In this virtual three-phase framework of phase m , $3P_m^*$ and $3Q_m^*$ represent the three-phase power references of each phase, being the current set-points at the POI $i_{s,m\alpha}^*$ and $i_{s,m\beta}^*$ defined as:

$$i_{s,m\alpha}^* = 2 \frac{P_m^* v_{s,m\alpha} - Q_m^* v_{s,m\beta}}{v_{s,m\alpha}^2 + v_{s,m\beta}^2} \quad \forall m = a, b, c, \quad (2)$$

$$i_{s,m\beta}^* = 2 \frac{P_m^* v_{s,m\beta} - Q_m^* v_{s,m\alpha}}{v_{s,m\alpha}^2 + v_{s,m\beta}^2} \quad \forall m = a, b, c$$

Fig. 2. Proposed strategy for independent power control per phase in 3P-4W VSC.

Once these virtual references of phase m have been computed, it is required to undo the change returning to the real system. For doing so, the virtual α component is associated with the reference current of its corresponding phase:

$$i_{sa}^* = i_{s,a\alpha}^* \quad i_{sb}^* = i_{s,b\alpha}^* \quad i_{sc}^* = i_{s,c\alpha}^* \quad (3)$$

and the neutral current is computed as:

$$i_{sn}^* = -(i_{sa}^* + i_{sb}^* + i_{sc}^*). \quad (4)$$

The above equations provide the real system reference currents in the phase domain which can be converted to the $\gamma\alpha\beta$ domain to perform the current tracking by means of resonant controllers [15]. Fig. 2 shows the proposed strategy for independent power control per phase.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section is devoted to validate the proposed independent per-phase power control described in the above section through simulation results. A 3P-4W VSC with a LCL filter for phases abc and an inductor in the neutral wire, as shown in Fig. 1, is implemented in MATLAB&Simulink. The power converter is connected to a balanced 3P-4W voltage source emulating a LV grid. The relevant parameters and control gains of the simulation are summarized in the Table I.

The controller is evaluated by incremental step reference changes at each of the powers P_m^* and Q_m^* . These steps are made progressively every 0.5 s in the simulation with the aim of analyzing the dynamic response of each power and its

interaction with the rest of the powers in the system. The initial and final references chosen for each phase as well as the time instant that the steps occur are collected in the Table II. Note that the references are completely different between the phases where injection and absorption of power coexist. In addition, the references have been established to demonstrate that they can operate in the four quadrants and the step reference also consider change of direction of the active and reactive power flows in some phases.

The reference and actual powers of each phase are shown in Fig. 3. The actual power per phase has been calculated from the RMS value of the current and voltage and the phase difference between them for each phase. Firstly, it can be seen that each actual power is able to track its reference properly with a smooth response during the transient. In addition, it can be observed that the reference change of the active power in phase m slightly distorts the reactive power of that phase and vice versa. This implies that there is some coupling between the active and reactive power of each phase m . However, it

TABLE I
PARAMETERS AND CONTROL GAINS IN THE SIMULATION.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
VSC side inductance	L_t	2.5 mH
VSC side resistance	R_t	0.08 Ω
Grid side inductance	L_s	2.5 mH
Grid side resistance	R_s	0.08 Ω
Filter capacitance	C	1 μ F
Neutral inductance	L_n	5 mH
Neutral inductance	R_n	0.16 Ω
Rated power of the VSC	S_n	20 kVA
AC rated voltage of the VSC	U_n	400 V
DC rated voltage of the VSC	v_{dc}	750 V
AC voltage of the LV grid	v_g	400 V
Frequency of the LV grid	f	50 Hz
Proportional gain	k_p	10 A/V
Resonant gain	k_r	314 A/V

TABLE II
ACTIVE AND REACTIVE POWER REFERENCE IN EACH PHASE.

Power	Initial Value	Final Value	Time (s)
P_a^*	7 kW	2 kW	1.0
Q_a^*	-2 kvar	-2 kvar	1.5
P_b^*	-5 kW	0 kW	2.0
Q_b^*	2 kvar	0 kvar	2.5
P_c^*	3 kW	-3 kW	3.0
Q_c^*	1 kvar	-1 kvar	3.5

Fig. 3. Tracking of the active and reactive powers for each phase. Top plot: Active and reactive power of phase a . Middle plot: Active and reactive power of phase b . Bottom plot: Active and reactive power of phase c

Fig. 4. Top plot: Tracking of the currents in the $\gamma\alpha\beta$ domain. Bottom plot: Actual currents injected by the VSC in its natural frame $abcn$.

is important to emphasize that the change in the active and reactive power reference in one phase does not affect the others, which means that the powers are completely decoupled between the phases.

The tracking of the power references, as well as their dynamic behavior and the decoupling between phases, is achieved thanks to the current references and the current tracking obtained according to the proposed control strategy. The top plot of Fig. 4 shows the reference and actual currents in the $\gamma\alpha\beta$ domain at the time instant 1.5 s. This coincides with the reactive power reference change Q_a^* . From a tracking point of view, a slight overshoot is observed in the actual currents, which is quickly corrected until the reference currents are reached in less than 5 cycles. The reference current i_{sb}^* and therefore the current i_{sb} are maintained constant despite the change in Q_a^* . This is because the current in the β axis is related to the active power, whereas the current in the α axis is directly related to the reactive power.

The currents injected into the POI in the $abcn$ domain are depicted in the bottom plot of Fig. 4. These currents show a completely unbalanced behavior as expected from the reference powers. The dynamic response behaves the same way as the currents in the $\gamma\alpha\beta$ domain. In addition, it is observed that only the current of phase a is affected at time instant 1.5s, leaving the other phases bc undisturbed. This is because the modified reference power in that instant time corresponds to the reactive power of that phase. Finally, it is important to note that the current of greatest magnitude is the current circulating through the neutral wire i_{sn} achieving up to twice the value with respect to the phases of the system.

Fig. 5. Devices involved in the experimental testbed

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A testbed consisting of a 20 kVA 3P-4W VSC is used to evaluate the performance of the proposed controller in an experimental environment as shown in Fig. 5. The DC side of the VSC is controlled by a DC source which maintains a DC voltage value equal to 730 V. The AC side is connected to a controllable AC source through an LCL filter and the neutral wire with an inductor as shown in Fig. 1. The AC source sets a balanced AC voltage at 230 V rms phase-to-neutral voltage and a frequency of 50 Hz. The parameters are identical to the simulation results and are summarized in Table I.

The VSC is subjected to two tests consisting of a change in the active and reactive power references of one of the system phases. This allows to evaluate the VSC's ability to track references and the degree of decoupling with the powers of the rest of the phases.

With respect to the first test, the VSC is initially operating in a balanced manner with 3 kW and 0 kvar as power references per phase as illustrated in Fig. 6. At the time instant $t = 0.06$ s, a step change in the active power reference P_c^* is produced from 3 kW to 4 kW. At the beginning of the test, the currents are balanced, the neutral current is zero and the active and reactive powers per phase are equal as expected. However, since the power reference change of P_c^* turns the currents unbalanced by increasing the phase c of the current. As a consequence, the neutral current is no longer zero from $t = 0.06$ s. Note that the only current affected under the reference change is the phase c , keeping the currents of phase a and b unchanged. The total harmonic distortion (THD) of the injected currents is below 1.33 % and 1.46% in the balanced and unbalanced scenarios respectively. With respect to the powers, the performance of the controller is good both from a steady-state and dynamic points of view. It is able to track the reference change achieved in less than one cycle as shown in the top and bottom plot of Fig. 6. The rest of the powers are barely affected with a slight disturbance at $t = 0.06$ s. Note that powers of each phase shown in the bottom plot of Fig. 6 have been obtained applying a low-pass filter to their corresponding instantaneous value to remove the oscillating 100 Hz term. This causes a slower dynamics in the shown time evolution.

Fig. 6. Step reference change of P_c^* for evaluation of the 3P-4W VSC independent power control per phase. Top plot: Instantaneous $abcn$ currents. Bottom plot: Filtered active and reactive power per phase.

The second test consists on applying a step change of the reactive power reference Q_c^* . Initially, the VSC is operated in a balanced manner with setpoints 3 kW and 0 kvar per each phase as shown in Fig. 7. As it can be observed, the currents are balanced and the current flowing through the neutral wire is zero. At $t = 0.06$ s, Q_c^* is changed from 0 kvar to 1 kvar leading to an unbalance system and causing a variation of the phase c current and neutral current circulation. Once again, an adequate monitoring of the powers is observed in each phase and a slight coupling with the rest of the powers.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has addressed the independent per-phase power control for three-phase four-legs VSCs. DSOs may take advantage of this ancillary service provided by already existing VSCs to reduce the voltage imbalance of the distribution network without resorting to additional investments in new control assets. For doing so, the DSO has to compute the required phase active and reactive power references in a centralized manner considering global network information by solving an optimization problem. Therefore, it is mandatory to provide a local VSC control algorithm that, using these phase power setpoints, compute the required reference current. This is not an straightforward task, since unbalanced power references lead to oscillatory power terms, which difficult the computation of the reference currents. To overcome this shortcoming, this work proposes to use a virtual three-phase system related to each phase which has been validated through simulation and experimental results.

Fig. 7. Step reference change of Q_c^* for evaluation of the 3P-4W VSC independent power control per phase. Top plot: Instantaneous $abcn$ currents. Bottom plot: Filtered active and reactive power per phase.

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